

A Statement on “Cascading” Christianity and Ancient Gospel Studies: A Reflection and an Invitation

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The following statement is based on a letter of support that I submitted to Dr. Mark Bilby’s university in support of his current research project. After sharing this letter with Dr. Bilby, I was asked if I would be willing to share this publicly in a slightly modified form. Given my excitement about the potential of this project, I have made the following available in order to encourage further development of this project in the field of biblical studies.

Dr. Mark Bilby has initiated a new research on the New Testament Gospels, notably drawing upon the non-canonical *Gospel of Marcion*. His unique and significant use of this understudied Gospel, as well as his methodological approach to not only resolving the literary relationship of the NT Gospels but also to our reconstruction of the history of early Christianity, carries the potential to transform our field of study. It is my hope that a collective of scholars will join together to explore, test, and extend beyond Dr. Bilby’s proposed research.

I’ve known Dr. Bilby for many years and I have always been impressed with both his scholarship and his integrity as a researcher. We have spent many hours, both in person and via phone, discussing and debating the history of early Christianity as well as the theoretical and methodological challenges facing our field. I was also the person who recommended Dr. Bilby as a contributor to the More New Testament Apocrypha project (MNTA), headed up by Professor Tony Burke with significant volumes published through Eerdmans. Dr. Bilby is an outstanding and gifted scholar.

It came to my attention that his “First Gospel” project has come under some criticism, allegedly by an administrator outside our field of study who made the mistaken analogy between Dr. Bilby’s work and some recent problems our field has dealt with regarding modern forgeries of

ancient texts. The most famous instance, of course, is the *Gospel of Jesus' Wife* fragment that was quickly and definitively identified as a late 20th-century production. Given my own research in Nag Hammadi and Gnosticism, I am very familiar with that debate and, even though I never published my views, I was engaged with a few people involved in the debate. From I know of Dr. Bilby's project, we are dealing with two very different situations. In one, we have a text that was fabricated in modern times and passed off (for a short period) as an ancient text. In the other, we have a scholar engaged in source criticism, endeavoring to uncover a lost source embedded within extant sources. What Dr. Bilby is doing in "discovering" a new gospel is not what happened in the case of Professor Karen King, who was duped into accepting this fragment as a fragment of an ancient Coptic gospel. (I have a great deal of respect and admiration for Dr. King's work and I am convinced that she was unaware of the fabricated nature of the fragment she was working on until after it had been made public.)

Rather, Mark Bilby is doing what we call source criticism, where one attempts to recover underlying sources no longer extant but embedded within extant texts. We do this all the time in biblical studies, notably with the Gospels (canonical and non-canonical). In unravelling the literary relationship between the Synoptic Gospels (and sometimes also incorporating the Gospel of John in such analyses), such hypothetical or recovered sources are valuable tools in "filling in the gaps" for explaining such textual relations. One of the most ambitious areas of such scholarship is Q scholarship, notably the creation of a critical edition in the 1990s under the leadership of Professor John Kloppenborg.

Q scholarship – or any other research into hypothetical or recovered texts – is always embraced by some scholars and approached with caution by other scholars. Some scholars see these as *real* texts that have been discovered or recovered (most Q scholars I've talked to view and treat Q in this way; so also with the Signs Source or Signs Gospel embedded within the Gospel of John), while others treat such texts as merely *hypothetical placeholders* or *heuristic devices* to solve textual problems. Despite the necessity of positing such sources in Gospel studies, such scholarship has always faced serious methodological problems and theoretical pitfalls (largely arising from a canonical bias in historical research). Dr. Bilby's work fits into this stream of Q scholarship, while addressing these research challenges.

I have not had a chance to read everything Dr. Bilby has written (he's produced a massive and impressive amount of detailed research to make his argument and I am still working through this material), but based on what I have read and our many discussions on this project, I believe that his work is potentially the most innovative and cutting-edge work to arise in Gospel studies in nearly a century. What sets his work apart from other efforts – and there have been many such efforts over the years, offering various advantages or disadvantages for our understanding of these texts and their place in the formation and history of earliest Christianity – is the

methodological sophistication and interdisciplinary application of acoustical methods in tracing linguistic echoes in the texts. He does not treat these texts as *singular moments* of literary dependence (i.e., does Matthew and Luke use Mark and Q or does Luke use Matthew and Mark, etc.?), but rather he identifies *a series of “cascading” moments* of textual activation and literary production between these texts, thereby allowing these texts to be studied as *malleable works* continually being received, interpreted, and modified in antiquity until they are more firmly set as monolithic works by ca. 200 CE (or the 180s CE when Irenaeus wrote his *magnus opus*). This cascading approach, even more than the acoustical method used, is a paradigm shift in our study of these texts (and, I think, potentially resolve the problem of minor agreements in Synoptic studies by not limiting the literary interaction to a singular moment of production or redaction). Dr. Bilby’s approach does the follow (in my opinion):

1. It strives for scientific precision that moves us away from subjective hermeneutics (in 19th century German NT scholarship, this was Higher Criticism, though Dr. Bilby attempts to use more modern research techniques rather than relying on philological methods). Recent Gospels scholarship tends to move away from the meticulous scientific efforts of these 19th and early 20th century scholars, with the unfortunate result that biblical scholarship is often (though not always) reduced to merely hermeneutical interpretations that are not grounded within detailed historical and linguistic models.

2. It better situates the study of the Gospels, and especially the reconstruction of Q, within ancient practices of literary production and reception. I have long been an advocate of situating our ancient texts within the cultural, religious, and social context(s) within which they emerged and were used. To study these texts as products of late antiquity, we must also study them as part of the late antiquity. Dr. Bilby allows us to explore ancient textual production, reception, and redaction/activation as modes of production for these early Christian texts.

3. It breaks down the canonical bias that has plagued biblical studies, by treating the *Gospel of Marcion* as a key source for establishing Q (rather than treating it as derivative of Luke). Throughout my career I have striven to get my students and colleagues to see the non-canonical and canonical sources as equally vital as historical sources for our historical reconstructions. To study “canon” in the second century is to study not a fixed collection of texts, but processes by which such a collection was established by ancient social actors. Too often, scholars tend to treat our historical sources as falling into two distinct blocks, with a chronological preference given to one over the other. Such a model emerges from modern confessional concerns and claims of orthodoxy. This model, furthermore, fails to appreciate the literary complexity of our sources as well as the oral and written processes by which such texts were produced and revised within communities.

4. It breaks new ground not only in the historical reconstruction of the formation of the NT Gospels, but, more importantly, in highlighting the cascading process of such formation. As a scholar of early Christianity, I am most excited by this new perspective (and I think it will help us better understand other early Christian texts). By tracing “echoes” in these texts, with fresh echoes being created through use, interpretation, and revisiting of previous material, each “activation” of a Gospel generates a new, rhizomatic product leading to further “Gospel rhizomes” – as if the gospels, over several decades, continued to intersect each other within a cultural and social “echo chamber”.

5. It offers an important new perspective on the non-canonical *Gospel of Marcion*. This Gospel has received almost no attention in biblical scholarship, often relegated to the margins in our field with only a few specialists working on this text as just one more apocryphal work standing of the fringe of biblical research. Recent scholarship has highlighted the significance of the *Gospel of Marcion* for tracing redactional versions of Luke (or *Ur-Luke*) (moving beyond Bultmann’s significant work, Tyson and Roth’s respective work comes readily to mind, though Roth treats the *Gospel of Marcion* differently than Bilby or Tyson) – and Dr. Bilby’s work builds on and extends such research. Regardless of the acceptance or rejection of Dr. Bilby’s treatment of this Gospel, as a result of his work scholarship will be forced to seriously study this text with greater care than has been done in the past. This alone is an important contribution to scholarship.

Finally, let me stress that what Dr. Bilby is doing is part of a broader movement in scholarship that is just emerging – and one with which I am happy to identify. New Testament studies often treats our sources as the products of first-century communities, with second-century heterodoxy and diversity (and debates over orthodoxy) arising in the wake of these first-century developments. This model is driven by both a canonical bias as well as modern theological battles between Protestant and Catholic exegetes. Since the 1960s, but especially in the 1990s and 2000s, scholars have struggled against this historical model. Occasionally, critical theories have been applied to point out the biases driving such a model (e.g., King’s *What Is Gnosticism* [2003]). A few of us are now recognizing that “Christianity” – as a recognizable sect or set of sects striving to establish their social identity – really arose in the second, not the first century, though drawing upon, redacting, circulating, and interpreting first-century raw material to create something that offers social legitimacy to a particular second-century communal and theological identity vis-à-vis other such identities. Professor William Arnal, in a seminal article published back in *MTSR*, argued for such a shift in perspective, and many Acts scholars are now dating that NT narrative to the early second-century. This shift allows us to intersect *all* of our historical sources, tracing the formation of not only individual sources but also of collections of sources (resulting in a nascent NT canon arising by the end of the second century). What Bilby is doing could have a significant impact beyond just the NT Gospels. I’m already rethinking my own approach to the Pauline letter collection – inclusive of the canonical (undisputed and disputed) and apocryphal

letters – as this cascading and acoustical approach may add much to the rhizomatic model I’m currently developing using Gilles Deleuze.

With the Gospels, Dr. Bilby offers us the most coherent and challenging – and I’d add most ambitious – model I’ve yet to see that allows us to situate these texts (and any of their underlying hypothetical sources) within this new historiographic approach to the emergence of early Christianity. His cascading model allows us to see a dynamic, malleable, and socially interactive process for linking the final forms of these NT Gospels both to the second-century emergence of Christianity and the first-century matrix from which Christianity was sparked. Such a move allows us to intersect our “emerging” Christian sources – both inside and outside the NT – with the broader historical and political dynamics of the Roman world (notably Pliny, Tacitus, and Suetonius who seem to be the first to identify these religious sectarians as distinct from the broader Jewish communities [note that this is the earliest instance of the label “Christian” being applied to these sectarians and largely with a negative connotation and within a context of opposition]). His scientific method has the potential to allow literary interpretation to gain enhanced scientific precision, and thus plausibility, in our historical reconstruction of this ancient religion.

How will Dr. Bilby’s work be received? Knowing how conservative biblical scholars are – both confessionally and in accepting new models – I would speculate that there will be those who will resist his findings, regardless of the plausibility or refinement we find in his work. There will be push back, and there will be misunderstanding of his work (I could see some not fully understanding the complexity of the research and thus treating this as merely another “gospel chart” to add to the plethora already out there – such as the charts I use to introduce my students to the Synoptic Problem and academic models to solve that problem). More significantly, however, there will be those who will embrace and build on Dr. Bilby’s work. This is a very important project with the potential to be a major paradigm shift in Gospel research. I’ve encouraged him to also consider cognitive theories of blending and input fields, along with cognitive science of religion more broadly, as there is a growing interest in that theoretical approach to the study of religion and one that needs to be more fully applied to early Christian studies (e.g., the application of cognitive poetics to the *Gospel of Philip* and the *Exegesis on the Soul* by Hugo Lundhaug is an excellent example of the kind of scholarship we need). Dr. Bilby’s work is highly interdisciplinary. He is encouraging a closer intersection of historical research with information sciences. His approach is unique and potentially groundbreaking.

My hope is that other scholars will give this project careful attention and consideration. I also hope that researchers will join in on this project in a dynamic collaboration – testing, developing, and applying the theoretical and methodological approaches and research findings to other arenas in early Christian studies. A cascading model will need to incorporate more than just

“Gospels” or even “New Testament” texts in order to be effective in charting out early Christian history of the formative centuries of this religious movement. We will need to bring together scholarship on martyrdom, NT epistles, early Christian apologetics and polemics, Nag Hammadi, the so-called Apostolic Fathers, the heresiologists, as well as apocryphal writings in order to reassess the intersectional “echoing” of our sources, ancient personalities, and communities in late antiquity.

Such a project requires collaboration, rather than just being the “pet project” of one scholar. I know that Dr. Bilby is trying to form a collaborative research group to refine and extend this project. I have encouraged him to formalize such a research group either as a unit within one of our major professional associations (e.g., SBL, CBA, or SNTS) or as an independent group (such as the Context Group or the Jesus Seminar). Dr. Bilby deserves to be given the chance to pursue this project with the full support and collaboration of his colleagues in the field of biblical studies and early Christian studies. I believe that Dr. Bilby has effectively brought together his well-established expertise in biblical studies and library-information studies to launch a fascinating and vital contribution to our field. I am looking forward to seeing where this project goes and the lively scholarly debates that inevitably arise – not only the agreements on research findings, but even more the disagreements and fresh perspectives that will erupt through such conversations and collaborations. I hope that readers of my statement will also recognize the significance of this project. It really is an exciting project.